

Position paper: The object biography as a model for documenting and integrating heterogeneous and multidisciplinary object data in the context of NFDI4Objects and beyond

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NFDI4Objects Task Area 6 Qualification, Harmonisation & Integration

Introduction

The digital transformation in the humanities and cultural sciences is leading to a fundamental reorientation of collection and object documentation. The German National Research Data Infrastructure for the Material Remains of Human and Environmental History (NFDI4Objects) is a science-driven initiative dedicated to the task of converting heterogeneous and interdisciplinary data on the material heritage of human and environmental history into sustainable, interoperable, and accessible forms. In NFDI4Objects, the concepts of the data life cycle and object biography form the central basis on which the consortium is structurally oriented. While the data life cycle (data creation, data processing, data analysis, data publication, data archiving) is a common principle in research data management, the object biography lays the foundation for a new understanding of the creation and representation of collection data. It links historical, archaeological, scientific, and museum perspectives and provides a structure in which the object is understood as a dynamic hub of events, actors, places, and meanings. The object biography is therefore not a purely narrative concept, but a paradigm for data modeling that transfers the semantics of material culture into digital knowledge systems (Gerber, Görz, Wagner 2025).

1. Theoretical foundations and scientific context

The concept of object biography, introduced by anthropologist Igor Kopytoff (1986), understands objects as carriers of their own “life stories,” whose meaning changes in social contexts. The concept has been applied primarily in material culture research, ethnology, and archaeology (see, for example, Joy 2009; Krmnicek 2009). These disciplines use the term metaphorically to reconstruct the “life story” of objects and thus reveal processes of appropriation, use, exchange, and change in meaning. Later, the concept was also deepened

in terms of cultural history, and its applicability to art and cultural studies research was emphasized (e.g., Boschung, Kreuz, Kienlin 2015). Finally, object biography was tested as a methodological tool for accessing material sources and reconstructing historical collection contexts (Braun 2015; Becker, Dolezel, Knittel, Stört, Wagner 2023), including in the digital realm (Wagner 2023).

NFDI4Objects adapts this concept in the form of a digital, semantic modeling approach for material cultural heritage. The aim is to design object biographies not only as narrative descriptions, but as structured, machine-readable information networks. The scientific basis for this is provided by the event-centered reference model CIDOC CRM (ISO 21127)¹ from the International Council of Museums and its extensions, which are implemented in the NFDI4Objects Object Ontology (N4O OO)². CIDOC CRM is an ontology that allows the creation, modification, use, research, and contextualization of objects to be described as events and these events to be linked to actors, places, time periods, and sources. The object biography thus forms the epistemological and technical interface between collection documentation, research, and digital data integration (Gerber, Görz, Wagner 2025). In the context of NFDI4Objects, in addition to physical objects such as collection items, buildings, and immovable furnishings, e.g., stained glass windows, digital twins of objects are also recorded.

2. A data model for object biographies

At the center of the model is the object as an entity (E22 Human-Made Object), whose “life cycle” is structured by events: creation or manufacture, use, encounter (including discoveries, finds, excavations, etc.), collection, research, modification, change of ownership, reception, current location, and, if applicable, destruction. These events (E5 Event, E7 Activity, E12 Production, etc.) are related to actors (E21 Person, E39 Group), places (E53 Place), and time periods (E52 Time Span).

The object biography thus becomes a network of interconnected entities whose semantic relationships are represented precisely and in depth and, at the same time, can be interpreted over the long term thanks to standard-based modeling. The event structure also allows uncertainties and ambiguities to be mapped, for example through assignment events (E13 Attribute Assignment), in which alternative interpretations can be documented and the meaning and significance of the objects can be presented in their historicity. This approach allows sources, provenance data, and research documentation to be linked in a knowledge graph that makes changes in meanings and contexts traceable, as has already been tested in previous projects (Wagner, Stört, Knittel 2024/Wagner 2023). The digital data

¹ See <https://cidoc-crm.org/versions-of-the-cidoc-crm> [Access: January 12, 2026].

² See <https://github.com/nfdi4objects/n4o-ontology> [Access: January 12, 2026].

model makes it possible to trace every statement about an object back to its source and author. In this way, information provenance—i.e., the traceability of knowledge creation—becomes a structural component of object documentation. Finally, the documentation and representation model for object biographies is particularly relevant for material cultural heritage in terms of provenance research and the associated reappraisal of so-called contexts of injustice, their transparent presentation, and the involvement of societies of origin in the generation of knowledge (Kultusministerium 2020/Deutscher Museumsbund 2023/Dubova, Wagner 2023/Kaiser, Heumann 2025).

3. Interdisciplinarity and implementation within the framework of NFDI4Objects

In NFDI4Objects, the object biography acts as an interdisciplinary link between specialist disciplines that have previously worked with different documentation standards and data formats. Archaeology, art history, restoration, materials science, ethnology, monument preservation, and natural sciences each generate their own research data, the integration of which has previously failed due to a lack of semantic compatibility. The object biography offers a common frame of reference that integrates these heterogeneous data via event structures from the CIDOC CRM, standard data (e.g., GND, VIAF, Wikidata, Getty Vocabularies), and controlled vocabularies (Bibby et al. 2023).

In Task Area 6 of NFDI4Objects (“Qualification, Harmonization & Integration”), the FAU Competence Center for Research Data and Information and the Klassik Stiftung Weimar are working with the community to develop the NFDI4Objects Object Ontology and the associated data model for object biographies based on use cases (Wagner, Gerber, Görz 2025a, b).³ The technical implementation of the data model for object biographies and their digital indexing is carried out in the virtual research environment WissKI⁴, which functions as an open, modularly expandable platform for semantic data modeling. An instance of WissKI was set up at the FAU CDI for NFDI4Objects.⁵ The individual components of the object biography are recorded in WissKI in forms whose fields are designated by collection documentation-related and scientific categories (in addition to inventory number or designation, categories such as iconographic motif, taxon, stratigraphy of a find, etc.) that are defined by the data model. The definition is based on so-called ontology paths, which consist of linked triple sequences of the form concept-property-concept. These semantic paths are set up and implemented in WissKI using the so-called Pathbuilder module. In addition, the Pathbuilder allows the CIDOC CRM-based event structure to be transferred to

³ For more information see <https://github.com/nfdi4objects/n4o-ontology> [Access: January 12, 2026].

⁴ See <https://wiss-ki.eu/de> [Access: January 12, 2026].

⁵ See <https://nfdi4objects.wisski.data.fau.de/> [Access: January 12, 2026].

user-friendly entry and search interfaces. The recorded data is made available directly as Linked Open Data in accordance with the FAIR principles (Fichtner 2025, Wagner 2024).

4. Scientific and societal added value

The data model for object biographies offers a wide range of scientific and strategic advantages:

- **Contextuality:** Event-based modeling allows changes in meaning and function to be traced.
- **Interoperability:** The use of international standards and vocabularies guarantees connectivity to existing systems.
- **Information provenance:** Every statement can be traced back to its source, author, and context.
- **Sustainability:** Events and their metadata are machine-readable and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) in the long term.
- **Extensibility:** The model is open to new event types, object types, and disciplines.
- **Participation:** It allows perspectives from societies of origin or the public, as well as current research results, to be included in object biographies.

These characteristics make the object biography not only a tool for documentation, but also a model of knowledge for interdisciplinary discourse on material culture. The concept enables an integrative perspective that goes beyond the classic collection description (Gerber, Görz, Wagner 2025). Instead of viewing an object in isolation in a museum context, its social, economic, and epistemic contexts are made visible. Ultimately, the biographies generated on this basis would constitute an essential source for provenance research.

5. The object biography as a future model for data integration

Semantic data integration is becoming increasingly important in the digital transformation of the humanities. The object biography serves as a model for linking data from different sources and phases in an object's life. It integrates primary data from archaeological excavations, findings and laboratory analyses, restorations, and archival research, as well as secondary data from publications and digital editions. In this way, it contributes to the creation of a networked research ecosystem that enables the reuse, analysis, and visualization of object data. Within the framework of the NFDI, the object biography thus becomes a central hub for the development of a federated, interoperable cultural heritage data space in Germany. In addition, the model has international connectivity: it is closely linked to initiatives such as Europeana, ARIADNEplus, and DARIAH-EU and contributes to the European research data strategy. On a methodological level, it opens up new

possibilities for data science, machine learning, and semantic network analysis in the field of material culture. This means that not only individual objects, but entire collection contexts, networks of actors, and historical processes can be researched on the basis of data.

6. Conclusion

The object biography is more than a theoretical construct—it is a paradigm that guides action for the future documentation, research, and communication of cultural heritage. It combines historical depth with digital precision, disciplines with infrastructures, and narrative with semantic forms of knowledge. As a data model within NFDI4Objects, it fulfills a dual function: it is a methodological tool for scientific reflection and, at the same time, the technical basis for data integration. It also creates a meta-level of knowledge about objects – an “integrative data modeling” that locates cultural objects in their contexts and makes their meanings reconstructable. It thus represents a paradigm shift for a new phase in the digital humanities: interdisciplinary, open, networkable, and sustainable.

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